

emerged *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens* brachyp-
 eters were examined. The following varia-
 tions in karyotypic features were de-
 tected:

1. Although females yield only one type of ova and males produce two types of sperm in both species, variations exist in the diploid chromosomal complement and the sex-determining mechanism (see table and figure).
2. In both species, chromosomes in gonial meiosis do not have distinct centromeres because they have dif-
 fused kinetochores. The constrictions vital for chromosomal movements and segregations during the meiotic stages are located along the length of the chromosomes. However, *N. bakeri* has relatively longer chromosomes: the shortest and the longest *N. bakeri* chromosomes are nearly 4 times longer than those of *N. lugens*. The nucleolar organizer of *N. bakeri* is its longest (143.50 mm) chromosome. In *N. lugens* it is 20.75 mm long.

These cytogenetic deviations impose pre- and post-mating barriers to effective hybridization between *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens*, and are additional taxonomic indices for differentiating the two species. □

Autosomes and sex chromosomes of planthopper species from *Leersia hexandra* (L.) Swartz. Sex chromosomes are indicated by arrows.

Incidence of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål on IR50 at graded levels of fertilization at Aduthurai

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IR50 was recently introduced in Tamil Nadu. We studied the response of this variety under graded levels of fertilization and BPH damage in a randomized block design with eight treatments and three replications. BPH population was recorded 80 d after transplanting (see table).

BPH population increased with fertilizer levels. Maximum BPH/hill was 106 when 150 kg N/ha was applied. The BPH population was lowest (5/hill) when no fertilizer was applied. P and K did not significantly influence BPH population.

Incidence of BPH under graded levels of fertilization, Aduthurai, India.

Fertilization ^a			BPH (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)
N	P	K		
0	0	0	5	4.1
50	0	0	50	4.7
100	0	0	53	5.5
150	0	0	106	4.6
50	11	21	28	4.7
100	22	42	54	5.4
150	33	62	84	5.0
0	22	42	5	5.0
CD			47.8	1.0

^aFertilization: 50% N = basal application, 25% N = topdressing at tillering, 25% N = topdressing at panicle initiation; P and K = basal applications.

At 100 kg N/ha with or without P and K, yield was 5.5 t/ha although the BPH population was above the economic threshold level. □

Effect of carbofuran and nitrogen on leaf-folder incidence

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The effects of combined application of carbofuran and nitrogen on leaf-folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (G.) incidence was studied at Tamil Nadu RRI Sep 1982-Jan 83. The field trial was in a split-plot design with three replications. Thirty-day-old IR20 seedlings were planted in 20-m² plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Carbofuran was incorporated at 0.5 and 0.75 kg ai/ha with a basal application of nitrogen as urea at planting. Carbofuran was topdressed at 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0 kg ai/ha with the first topdressing of urea 15 days after transplanting (15 DT). N levels 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha were applied

Effect of carbofuran application on leaffolder incidence, Aduthurai, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Leaffolder damage (%)
Control	27.1
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	24.5
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	21.1
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	26.4
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	19.7
1.0 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	17.6
CD	NS

to subplots in 3 splits – 50% basal, 25% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Leaffolder incidence on 10 hills/plot was recorded at 60 DT by counting the total and damaged leaves and calculating the percentage.

Method of carbofuran application did not significantly influence leaffolder incidence. However, topdressing of carbo-

Effect of nitrogen level on leaffolder incidence.

furan at 15 DT caused a slight decrease in the pest incidence (see table). Increased levels of nitrogen application caused a

corresponding increase in pest population (see figure). Carbofuran-nitrogen interaction was not significant. □

A new predaceous beetle of whitebacked planthopper in India

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Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) is a potentially destructive rice pest during kharif in Madhya Pradesh. Populations are suppressed by several enemies including mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. Staphylinid beetle *Paederus fuscipes* Curtis (Staphylinidae: Coleoptera) is a predator of brown planthopper (BPH) in Malaysia, Japan, Taiwan, and Thailand. Two species of this beetle, *P. fuscipes* and *P. melampus* Er., feed on BPH in India.

Large populations (25-30 beetles/hill) of staphylinid beetle *P. fuscipes* were found in fields in Apr 1981, feeding on WBPH nymphs. In confinement the beetles also preferred nymphs. This is the first record of *P. fuscipes* in M. P., India. □

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to light sources

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Gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is a major rice pest in India and in Tamil Nadu State. Infestations occur from Aug to Feb with maximum populations between Sep and Nov. Gall midge attraction to different light sources and light traps

was studied at the Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai. A bamboo trap with a 40W incandescent bulb, a bamboo trap with a 250W infrared lamp, and a Robinson type trap with a 125W mercury vapor lamp were set up in a triangle over the field. The trap positions were randomly interchanged each day after morning counts. Total weekly gall midge catches were combined over 4 weeks and compared.

The bamboo trap with 250W infrared light source attracted the most insects, followed by the 40W incandescent light

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to different light sources, Madurai, India, 1981.

Week ending	40W incandescent lamp	250W infrared lamp	125W HPL mercury vapor lamp
19 Sep 81	149 (2.17)	360 (2.56)	69 (1.84)
26 Sep 81	120 (2.08)	258 (2.41)	35 (1.54)
3 Oct 81	140 (2.15)	274 (2.44)	67 (1.83)
10 Oct 81	155 (2.19)	255 (2.41)	52 (1.72)
Total	(8.59)	(9.82)	(6.93)
Mean	(2.15)	(2.46)	(1.73)

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values.